

Advances in antibody-based strategies for targeting cancer-associated glycopeptide antigens

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The development of tumor-targeting antibodies has progressed tremendously over the past few decades, yet improving tumor selectivity and efficacy remains a challenge. Among tumor-associated antigens, tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs) have emerged as critical immunological targets because of their overexpression in malignant cells. However, the weak immunogenicity and structural homogeneity of carbohydrates pose obstacles for therapeutic antibody development. By designing antibodies to recognize epitopes that span both TACAs and adjacent amino acid residues on tumor glycoprotein surfaces, researchers can achieve higher specificity and functional efficacy while lowering on-target off-tumor related toxicities.

Keywords: tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens; glycosylation; cancer immunotherapy; Tn; STn; antibody discovery

Introduction

Cancer remains one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide and presents a formidable clinical challenge because of its complex biology and capacity for immune evasion. Over the past few decades, treatment strategies have evolved from nonspecific cytotoxic agents to more refined modalities that aim to selectively target malignant cells. Among these, monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) have emerged as a cornerstone of targeted cancer therapy, offering improved specificity, reduced systemic toxicity, and new avenues for immune system engagement.

One of the key principles underpinning antibody-based immunotherapy is the selective recognition of molecular features that distinguish cancer cells from their healthy counterparts (Figure 1). Such features include tumor-associated antigens (TAAs), tumor-specific antigens (TSAs), and tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs).^{(p1),(p2),(p3),(p4)} Each of these antigen classes presents distinct opportunities and challenges for therapeutic exploitation. mAb-based therapies and chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-T-cell technologies have both leveraged these antigenic targets to achieve significant clinical benefits in

certain malignancies, marking important steps toward more personalized forms of cancer treatment.^{(p5),(p6),(p7)}

TAAs, typically proteins or glycoproteins that are overexpressed on tumor cells but still present at lower levels in normal tissues, have been successfully targeted in several approved therapies. For instance, trastuzumab, which is used in human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2)-positive breast cancer, demonstrates how differential expression can be harnessed for therapeutic gain.^(p8) Nevertheless, the partial presence of TAAs on healthy tissues introduces risks of off-target effects and toxicity, highlighting the need for more tumor-specific strategies.^(p9)

In contrast, TSAs originate from somatic mutations or the aberrant re-expression of embryonic genes, giving rise to so-called neoantigens.^{(p10),(p11)} These antigens are absent in healthy adult tissues, making them particularly attractive for immunotherapeutic applications. However, their clinical translation has faced several obstacles, including tumor heterogeneity, immune escape mechanisms, and the relatively infrequent and variable expression of oncofetal proteins across cancer types.

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FIGURE 1

Comparison of tumor-associated antigens (TAAs), tumor-specific antigens (TSAs), and tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs). Although TACAs are generally associated with tumors, based on cell surface expression patterns in normal versus malignant cells, their expression can range from TAA-like (shared with normal tissues) to TSA-like (cancer-specific), reflecting their heterogeneity in tumor specificity.

TACAs represent a distinct and comparatively underexplored category of tumor antigens.^{(p12),(p13)} These structures arise from the alterations in glycosylation pathways that frequently accompany malignant transformation. Aberrant activity of glycosyltransferases, impaired chaperone proteins such as core 1 β 1-3-galactosyltransferase-specific chaperone

(COSMC), and reorganization of glycosylation machinery within the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus can all contribute to the formation of these atypical glycans.^(p14) Structurally, TACAs frequently display tumor-restricted expression, with epitopes formed by the altered glycan and adjacent peptide surface more closely resembling TSAs than

TAAAs owing to their absence, or extreme rarity, in healthy adult tissues.^(p13) This molecular specificity renders them promising candidates for selective therapeutic intervention.

TACAs encompass a range of glycan structures, including truncated *O*-glycans such as Thomsen-nouveau (Tn), Thomsen-Friedenreich (TF), and sialyl-Tn (STn), aberrantly branched or sialylated *N*-glycans, and dysregulated glycosphingolipids like Globo H, ganglioside D2 (GD2), and Neu5Gc-GM3.^{(p12),(p15)} These antigens have been implicated in cancer progression, immune modulation, and metastatic potential. For instance, truncated *O*-glycans that are found on surface-exposed serine (Ser) and threonine (Thr) residues are observed in the majority of carcinomas and are associated with poor clinical outcomes.^{(p16),(p17)} Although they can be variable depending on the carrier protein, *N*-glycan changes are widely reported across solid tumors, whereas gangliosides such as GD2 are overexpressed in nearly all pediatric neuroblastomas, underscoring their potential as tumor-specific markers.^(p18)

Despite their biological relevance, therapeutic exploitation of TACAs has been relatively limited.^(p41) Their low immunogenicity and the structural similarity of some glycans to those found in normal tissues have posed challenges for drug development. However, the limited expression of many TACAs in healthy tissue, combined with their prevalence in certain tumor types, makes them attractive targets for mAbs, vaccines, and adoptive cell therapies such as CAR-T and CAR-natural killer (NK) cells.^{(p5),(p6),(p42),(p43),(p44)} Recent efforts to enhance binding specificity, such as the development of biparatopic antibodies that engage both TACAs and nearby peptide motifs, demonstrate how new molecular engineering tools can be used to overcome prior limitations in affinity and specificity.

This review focuses on the opportunities and challenges of using antibody-based modalities to target tumor-associated glycopeptide epitopes as a strategy for cancer immunotherapy. We discuss the unique selectivity offered by TACA-peptide recognition, summarize current preclinical and clinical efforts, including antibody-based, antibody-drug conjugate (ADC), and CAR-T approaches, and outline technological advances poised to accelerate the development of next-generation glycan-targeted therapeutics.

Targeting TACAs and TACA-peptide epitopes

The selective targeting of TACAs and their neighboring amino acid residues offers a unique strategy for cancer immunotherapy. Malignant transformation often results in the aberrant expression of truncated *O*-glycan structures, especially Tn and STn, that are virtually absent in healthy adult tissues.^(p45) In contrast to normal cells, which display fully branched and elongated *O*-glycan structures, these aberrant forms create unique epitopes close to the protein surface, enabling selective targeting.^{(p13),(p46),(p40)} This approach might be especially attractive when applied to glycoproteins essential for tumor viability, because tumor cells might be unable to downregulate such proteins without losing proliferative capacity. Furthermore, the restricted expression of tumor-associated glycoforms in normal tissue allows for the design of very high-affinity antibodies with reduced risk of off-tumor toxicity, addressing key limitations of TAA-based therapies.^(p47)

Recent preclinical and translational studies have underscored the viability of this approach.^{(p18),(p48),(p49)} Specifically, antibody-based modalities, including unmodified mAbs, ADCs, radioimmunoconjugates (RICs), and bispecific formats, are being developed to engage TACA-peptide epitopes.^(p50) For instance, GT-00AxIL15 from GlycoTope (Berlin, Germany), an interleukin (IL)-15-based immunocytokine, recently demonstrated *in vivo* efficacy against tumor-associated mucin 1 (TA-MUC1)-positive tumors.^(p37) Also, GO Therapeutics (Natick, MA, USA) reported a mAb, 4C8, targeting a cancer-specific, aberrantly *O*-glycosylated splice variant of cluster of differentiation (CD)44 (Tn-CD44v6), with high specificity in preclinical CAR-T cell models.^{(p40),(p51),(p24),(p25)} Meanwhile, the PankoMab series from GlycoTope offers clinical-stage proof of concept for Tn-MUC1-targeted strategies.^{(p52),(p53),(p54),(p55)}

These glycopeptide-dependent antibodies show markedly better specificity than those that bind glycans or peptides alone. Their dual requirement for aberrant glycan and peptide context limits binding to tumor-specific glycoforms. Examples include L2A5, selective for STn-MUC1; PODO447, recognizing a tumor-exclusive podocalyxin glycoform; and PankoMab-GEX (gatipotuzumab), which binds TA-MUC1 without off-target tissue staining. GT-002 and GT-008, from GlycoTope and directed against aberrantly glycosylated Ly6/PLAUR domain containing 3 (LYPD3) and CD24, respectively, also show no staining in healthy tissue, underscoring the potential safety of glycopeptide selectivity. Together, these agents illustrate how antibody engineering can reach levels of specificity suitable for clinical translation.

Beyond antibodies, industry is adapting this concept to ADCs and RICs (Table 1). Companies like Pentixapharm (Berlin, Germany), Siamab Therapeutics (Newton, MA, USA), and Tacalyx (Berlin, Germany) are advancing glycan-targeted ADCs with promising antitumor activity, though the precise glycoprotein epitopes remain confidential.^{(p49),(p26)} For instance, the humanized anti-STn ADC from Siamab has shown efficacy for ovarian carcinoma models.^(p27) Additionally, RICs, including those utilizing beta- and alpha-emitting isotopes, such as lutetium-177 and actinium-225, are under investigation by Pentixapharm, OncoTab (Charlotte, NC, USA), and others for their potential to deliver potent cytotoxic radiation directly to tumors while minimizing systemic exposure.^{(p56),(p57),(p58)} Though relatively few studies have been published,^(p59) information can be found via conference abstracts, posters, and news releases.

Cell-based therapies also contribute to this expanding field. CAR-T and CAR-NK cells engineered to recognize glycosylated epitopes represent an innovative direction for glycan-targeted immunotherapy. In this area, Posey *et al.* demonstrated that CAR-T cells directed against the Tn-glycoform of MUC1 (based on a 5E5 construct) could effectively control adenocarcinoma growth in preclinical models.^(p60) Subsequent work by Yazdanifar *et al.*, Zhou *et al.*, and others have reinforced the utility of glycan-specific CARs in overcoming immune resistance mechanisms linked to abnormal glycosylation.^{(p61),(p62),(p63)} Building on these findings, reviews by Nasiri *et al.* and Steentoft *et al.* highlight how these strategies could yield enhanced tumor specificity with potentially fewer off-target effects.^{(p7),(p64)}

TABLE 1

Antibodies targeting TACAs and TACA-glycopeptides.^a

Therapy (clone)	Format	Target TACA	Target type	Developer	Stage	Notes
Naxitamab (Danyelza)	mAb (IgG1)	GD2	Glycan	Y-mAbs Therapeutics	Approved	Humanized IgG1 anti-GD2. Approved for relapsed/refractory high-risk neuroblastoma. Similar target/safety as dinutuximab (neuropathic pain, capillary leak). Shorter infusion schedule (30–60 min) because of different binding kinetics. ^(p19)
GD2 CAR-T	CAR-T	GD2	Glycan	Stanford University (Mackall lab), University College London	Phase I NCT04196413 NCT05544526	Autologous CAR-T with anti-GD2 scFv (derived from 14G2a) and safety switch (RQR8). In a Phase I trial for H3K27M ⁺ diffuse midline glioma; 9/11 patients improved neurologically and 7 had tumor shrinkage (some dramatic). Median survival ~2 years.
Dinutuximab (Unituxin)	mAb (IgG1)	GD2	Glycan	United Therapeutics	Approved	Chimeric (mouse-human) IgG1 targeting GD2. FDA-approved for high-risk neuroblastoma. Improves EFS/OS but causes neuropathic pain (GD2 on nerves) and infusion reactions. Used in combination with IL-2, GM-CSF, and retinoic acid. ^(p20)
OBI-999	ADC (IgG–MMAE)	Globo H	Glycan	OBI Pharma	Phase I/II (advanced solid tumors) NCT04084366	OBI-999 = OBI-888 (anti-Globo H) linked to MMAE. Phase I (15 pts) found MTD 1.2 mg/kg; dose-limiting neutropenia at 1.6 mg/kg. 5/15 patients had stable disease (1 with >13 cycles). Development now in Phase II for Globo H ⁺ tumors. ^(p21)
OBI-888	mAb (IgG1)	Globo H	Glycan	OBI Pharma	Phase I/II (GI/solid tumors) NCT03573544	Humanized IgG1 against Globo H. Phase I/II (54 pts) showed safety up to 20 mg/kg, no MTD; 20–28% of patients achieved stable disease. Induced ADCC in patients (3–4× increase). Globo H is overexpressed on breast, gastric, and pancreatic cancers. ^(p22)
SGN-15	ADC (IgG3–doxorubicin)	Lewis Y	Glycan	Seattle Genetics	Phase II (NSCLC, discontinued) NCT00031187	Chimeric (human IgG3) anti-Le ^Y mAb conjugated to doxorubicin. In Phase II, NSCLC + docetaxel, SGN-15 arm had longer median OS (31.4 vs 25.3 week) and similar tolerability. Well-tolerated. No further development reported.
Hu3S193	mAb (IgG1)	Lewis Y	Glycan	Seattle Genetics	Phase I/II NCT00617773 NCT00072410	Humanized anti-Le ^Y IgG1. Phase I studies showed safety. Potent CDC/ADCC <i>in vitro</i> . Tested as naked mAb and in RIC. Binds many epithelial tumors; development paused after initial trials.
GT-001	mAb (IgG)	Lewis Y	Glycan	Glycotope	Preclinical	High-affinity anti-Le ^Y . Binds ~80–100% of human breast, NSCLC, CRC cell lines; internalizes well (suitable for ADC/CAR). Le ^Y expression largely tumor-restricted (type II fucosylated chain); no serious normal tissue binding reported. ^(p23)
HuMab-5B1 (MVT-5873)	mAb (IgG1)	Sialyl-Le ^A (CA19-9)	Glycan	Polaris/Leidos (Merck subsidiary)	Phase I (completed) NCT02672917	Fully human IgG1 to SLe ^A /CA19-9. Phase I trial in CA19-9 ⁺ GI tumors showed it was well-tolerated (no DLT) and elicited ADCC. Being tested alone or with chemo. Aims to block CA19-9-mediated tumor adhesion.

TABLE 1 (CONTINUED)

Therapy (clone)	Format	Target TACA	Target type	Developer	Stage	Notes
JAA-F11	mAb (murine/humanized IgG1)	TF	Glycan	For-Robin Inc	Preclinical/translational	Murine original was IgG3; humanized versions H2aL2a and H3L3 show selective binding to TF- α (not TF- β), internalization, and <i>in vivo</i> tumor suppression in lung and breast xenografts. ^{(p24),(p25)}
ST1	ADC (IgG-MMAE)	Sialyl-Tn	Glycan	Siamab Therapeutics	Preclinical	Humanized IgG1 conjugated to MMAE targeting STn. <i>In vitro</i> : potent killing of STn ⁺ tumor cells. <i>In vivo</i> : shrank STn ⁺ ovarian xenografts with no weight loss or toxicity. Also depletes STn ⁺ MDSCs in tumor (potential dual effect). ^{(p26),(p27),(p28)}
3F1	mAb (IgG2a)	Two adjacent STn (bis-STn motif)	Glycan	University of Washington (Hakomori)	Research control	Used as a control in several studies. First discovered via hybridoma technology following immunization of mice with ovine submaxillary mucin (OSM). ^(p29)
L2A5	mAb (IgG)	Sialyl-Tn	Glycopeptide	NOVA University (Novo and Videira)	Preclinical	Novel hybridoma-derived IgG targeting STn and α 2-6 sialylated short O-glycans. Flow/IHC: stains bladder, colorectal, TNBC cancers (including metastases) with high specificity; no normal tissue staining. Potential diagnostic/therapeutic tool. ^{(p30),(p31)}
G2D11	scFv	Two adjacent Tn residues (bis-Tn motif)	Glycopeptide	Copenhagen University (Blixt) Lund University (Danielsson and Jansson)	Preclinical (tool)	Derived from an immunized mouse phage display library. G2D11 targets two adjacent Tn residues (bis-Tn) displayed on a glycopeptide, with lower dependency on the peptide backbone sequence. Binding confirmed for three forms: Ser-Thr, Thr-Thr, and Thr-Ser. ^{(p32),(p33)}
PODO447	mAb (IgG)	Podocalyxin glycopeptide	Glycopeptide	University of British Columbia (McNagny)	Preclinical	Rabbit-derived IgG to a podocalyxin glycopeptide epitope. Binds >65% of high-grade serous ovarian tumors and other Podxl ⁺ cancers, but not normal endothelium/podocytes. ADC forms kill tumor cells <i>in vitro</i> ; no normal binding observed. ^{(p34),(p35)}
HuCC49 Δ CH2	mAb (IgG1 Δ CH2)	Tn/STn TAG-72	Glycopeptide	UAB/Centocor	Preclinical (radioimmunotherapy)	Humanized CC49 lacking CH2 domain; targets TAG-72. In mice, ¹⁷⁷ Lu-HuCC49 Δ CH2 gave much higher tumor:blood ratio and longer survival vs intact CC49. Explored for ovarian/colorectal (radio-IR) but not advanced clinically. ^(p36)
GT-00A	mAb (IgG1)	TA-MUC1	Glycopeptide	Glycotope/Daiichi-Sankyo	Preclinical (ADC, immunocytokine)	Binds a cancer-specific glycopeptide epitope on MUC1 (TA-MUC1) virtually absent on normal tissues. Developing as ADC and IL-15 immunocytokine (licensed to Daiichi). Shows tumor-selective binding; ideal for targeted payload delivery. ^(p37)
PankoMab-GEX (gatipotuzumab)	mAb (IgG1)	TA-MUC1	Glycopeptide	Biotest/Glycotope	Phase I/II (ovarian CA) NCT01222624	Humanized anti-TA-MUC1 IgG1 (glyco-engineered for high ADCC). Phase I: no MTD reached; well-tolerated with infusion reactions as DLTs. Clinical benefit in 25% of patients. Phase II in ovarian CA ongoing.

(continued on next page)

TABLE 1 (CONTINUED)

Therapy (clone)	Format	Target TACA	Target type	Developer	Stage	Notes
GT-008	mAb (IgG); RIC	TF-CD24	Glycopeptide	Glycotope/ Pentixapharm	Preclinical	Monoclonal IgG that selectively recognizes a tumor-specific O-glycoform of CD24, in which the epitope requires the truncated Thomsen–Friedenreich antigen.
GT-002	mAb (IgG)	TF-LYPD3	Glycopeptide	Glycotope	Preclinical	Monoclonal IgG that selectively recognizes a tumor-specific O-glycoform of LYPD3, in which the epitope requires the truncated Thomsen–Friedenreich antigen.
CART-TnMUC1	CAR-T	Tn/STn-MUC1	Glycopeptide	Tmunity Therapeutics/ University of Pennsylvania (Posey)	Phase I (ongoing) NCT04025216	Targets the cancer-specific Tn/STn glycoforms of MUC1; uses a novel CD2 co-stimulator to reduce exhaustion. Early trials show tumor shrinkage and stable disease without severe toxicity.
5E5	mAb (IgG)	Tn/STn-MUC1	Glycopeptide	Copenhagen University (Clausen)	Preclinical (tool)	Murine IgG1 (now humanized) specific for the core Tn-MUC1 epitope. High affinity and tumor specificity; structure of Fab bound to Tn-glycopeptide, confirming glycopeptide-dependent binding is available.
B72.3	mAb (IgG1)	Tn/STn-TAG-72	Glycopeptide	National Cancer Institute (Schlom)	Diagnostic (discontinued)	Murine mAb generated immunization with a membrane-enriched extract of a human mammary carcinoma biopsy.
TCX-101	ADC (IgG – MMAE)	TACA (undisclosed glycan)	Undisclosed	Tacalyx	Preclinical	ADC against a tumor-specific glycan. <i>In vitro</i> : kills pancreatic/colon cancer lines with sub-nM IC ₅₀ ; <i>in vivo</i> : regressed high-glycan xenografts. Exact antigen not public. Demonstrates potent activity (with MMAE payload) against multiple cancer types. ^(p38)
TCX-201	ADC (IgG–MMAE)	TACA (undisclosed glycan)	Undisclosed	Tacalyx	Preclinical	ADC against a tumor-associated glycan (distinct from TCX-101). Also showed potent killing of cancer cells and tumor regression in xenograft models. Antigen identity is proprietary. Represents a separate glycan target. ^(p39)
4C8	mAb (IgG)/ CAR format	Tn-CD44v6	Glycopeptide	GO Therapeutics	Preclinical	Binds Tn-glycosylated CD44v6 with low nM affinity; high cancer specificity by IHC, minimal staining in healthy skin; 4C8 CAR-T shows <i>in vivo</i> tumor regression and selective killing in mixed tissue models. ^(p40)

^a Abbreviations: ADCC, antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity; CA19-9, cancer antigen 19-9; CDC, complement dependent cytotoxicity; CRC, colorectal cancer; DLT, dose-limiting toxicity; EFS, event-free survival; OS, overall survival; GM-CSF, granulocyte–macrophage colony-stimulating factor; IgG, immunoglobulin G; IHC, immunohistochemistry; Le^A, Lewis A; Le^Y, Lewis Y; MDSC, myeloid-derived suppressor cells; MMAE, monomethyl auristatin E; MTD, maximum tolerated dose; NSCLC, non-small cell lung cancer; TAG, tumor-associated glycoprotein; TNBC, triple-negative breast cancer.

Across the abovementioned modalities, a common theme is emerging: glycopeptide-targeted strategies often yield superior selectivity compared with peptide-only approaches. By targeting epitopes that combine aberrant glycans with peptide context, one might be able to ‘unlock’ new glycoprotein targets once deemed undruggable. Together, these strategies spanning antibodies, ADCs, RICs, and CAR-based therapies represent a converging path toward highly selective, durable, and safer cancer immunotherapies.

Technological advances in the discovery of anti-TACA antibodies

The development of anti-TACA–peptide antibodies has been significantly enhanced by several technological advancements in recent years. These advances have not only enhanced the toolbox for identification of TACA-bearing recombinant proteins and improved antibody specificity, but have also dramatically shortened the process of discovering antibodies against these TACA-bearing proteins.

Advances in expression technologies

An advancement in the area of expression of TACA-containing recombinant proteins has been the development of SimpleCell technology, which involves genetically engineering mammalian cell lines to produce simplified *O*-glycosylation patterns, such as TF, Tn, and STn.^(p65) This approach not only enables comprehensive mapping of the *O*-GalNAc glycoproteome across several mammalian cell lines, as illustrated by Steentoft *et al.*, who mapped nearly 3,000 glycosylation sites across more than 600 glycoproteins, but also permits the recombinant expression of glycoproteins bearing truncated *O*-glycans.^{(p65),(p66),(p67),(p68)} Adaption of this methodology to other cell lines, though not widely reported in the literature, is particularly useful as it allows for the generation of immunogens that specifically display the desired aberrant glycan structures, thereby facilitating immunization campaigns, as shown by companies like Glycope.^(p69) Furthermore, by expressing not only the aberrantly glycosylated protein but also its normally glycosylated and deglycosylated counterparts as controls, researchers can rigorously screen antibody selectivity for those that bind exclusively to the tumor-associated isoforms.^{(p70),(p71)} This approach is useful for developing highly selective anti-TACA-peptide antibodies for both diagnostic and therapeutic applications.

Knowledge gained from structural characterization of anti-TACA antibodies

Several crystal structures now exist that help to define how TACA-specific mAbs engage *O*-glycopeptide epitopes: mono-Tn binders [e.g. 5E5, Protein Data Bank (PDB) 6TNP and 9ECI], clustered-Tn binders (G2D11, PDB 8S6K; 2D9, PDB 8S6V), mono-STn binders (L2A5; PDB 9FXT and 9FY8), and clustered-STn binders (3F1, PDB 8S6T; and CC49, PDB 1ZA6). In some cases, these structures reveal whether recognition is driven predominantly by direct contacts with the sugar(s), by interactions with the peptide backbone, or by a composite glycopeptide interface. Additionally, structures such as L2A5 help to explain differences in specificity and tolerance for Ser versus Thr linkages. Some antibodies show cross-reactivity between Tn and STn, or reduced affinity for one linkage over another (for example, 5E5 and CC49), highlighting the subtleties of glycan stereochemistry and local backbone conformation in epitope recognition. Combined structural and *in silico* analyses (paratope engineering and docking/molecular simulations), such as those done by Hurtado-Guerrero *et al.*,^(p33) provide key information required for rational affinity maturation, humanization, and the design of antibody-based modalities (ADCs, CARs, RICs) that selectively target tumor-restricted glycoforms.

As an example, structural insights from studies on the antibodies 5E5 and L2A5 have revealed how precise glycan coordination and binding pocket architecture determine specificity for TACAs. In a recent study, Macías-León *et al.* used X-ray crystallography to perform a detailed structural analysis of the anti-MUC1 antibody 5E5, which exhibits unique lectin-like properties.^(p72) The crystal structure revealed that the 5E5 antibody engages the Tn antigen through a unique binding interaction with the GalNAc residue. Specifically, GalNAc is oriented perpendicularly toward the binding pocket located at the interface between the heavy and light chains of the antibody.

This arrangement is key, as essentially all of the GalNAc hydroxyl groups are strongly coordinated by specific residues in the antibody, thus enforcing high specificity for the Tn antigen, thereby ensuring specificity for only the truncated glycan form (Figure 2). Notably, the O6 hydroxyl group is exposed to the solvent, which is a feature that explains the tolerance of the antibody for the STn antigen, albeit with greatly reduced affinity compared with the non-sialylated Tn.

In contrast, Soares *et al.* described another antibody, L2A5, which demonstrates high specificity for the STn antigen when bound to both Thr and Ser.^(p30) The crystal structure of L2A5 revealed a binding pocket that accommodates both the GalNAc and the adjacent sialic acid moiety deep within the interface of the heavy and light chains. Through a network of multiple hydrogen bonds and additional non-covalent interactions, L2A5 achieves robust and specific coordination with the entire STn epitope. This contrasts with other *O*-glycan TACA-targeting antibodies that tend to rely primarily on interactions with the peptide backbone of the antigens rather than with the carbohydrate moiety itself (for example, antibodies SM3, SN-101, and AR20.5).^{(p73),(p74),(p75),(p76)}

A key theoretical consideration in the design of anti-TACA antibodies is the impact of glycan chain length on antigen binding. In principle, with short TACAs, such as the Tn or STn antigens, the carbohydrate moiety can be precisely coordinated within the central binding pocket, thereby allowing the remaining complementarity-determining region (CDR) loops to interact with the nearby peptide surface of the target antigen. In contrast, elongated glycan chains might impede access to the peptide surface because of steric hindrance or altered antigen presentation (Figure 2). When antigen recognition is strongly mediated by the TACA, with peptide interactions serving a complementary role, this configuration could offer enhanced specificity for the aberrantly glycosylated version of the TAA while also potentially increasing overall affinity. However, extending this strategy to other glycan classes (particularly *N*-glycans) is more challenging, as these structures extend further from the protein surface and often exhibit substantial structural similarity to glycans present on healthy cells. The distinct binding modes of 5E5 and L2A5 underscore the potential for selective engagement of TACA epitopes through direct carbohydrate coordination. Unlike most *O*-glycan-targeting antibodies described to date, which predominantly interact with the peptide backbone,^(p74) these antibodies recognize TACAs primarily via the glycan itself. Their unique structural features highlight the value of continued structural elucidation to identify similar antibodies and inform the rational design of next-generation diagnostics and therapeutics targeting aberrant glycosylation.

Primary B-cell screening for the discovery of anti-TACA antibodies

Advancements in primary B-cell screening techniques have also been useful for the identification and validation of antibodies against TACAs. Kling Biotherapeutics (Amsterdam, The Netherlands) (formerly AIMM Therapeutics) has reported the discovery of two patient-derived antibodies currently undergoing preclinical development. The first, KBA1636, was isolated from a colon cancer survivor and targets a truncated, *O*-mannosylated variant

FIGURE 2

Structural basis for selectively targeting the Tn antigen by anti-TACA antibody 5E5 (PDB 6TNP). **(a)** Global view of the 5E5-Tn complex, showing the antibody bound in a perpendicular orientation relative to the Tn-MUC1 glycopeptide. **(b)** Close-up of the binding pocket reveals that the Tn antigen (GalNAc α -Ser/Thr) fits precisely within the shallow groove of the antibody, with no steric hindrance. **(c)** *In silico* model of a disialylated core 1 O-glycan docked into the 5E5 binding site. The extended glycan protrudes beyond the confines of the pocket, resulting in steric clashes that would preclude stable binding. **(d)** *In silico* model of a branched core 2 O-glycan with terminal sialic acid and fucose residues further demonstrates that elongated or branched O-glycans are incompatible with the binding mode of 5E5. Glycans other than Tn were modeled *in silico*. Sugar residues are colored as follows: N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) in orange, N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) in blue, sialic acid in magenta, fucose in red, and galactose in yellow. The peptide portion of the MUC1 glycopeptide is colored in light gray. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of E-cadherin.^(p77) The second, KBA1413, was derived from an acute myeloid leukemia (AML) survivor and recognizes a unique sialylated epitope on CD43, expressed across all AML subtypes, myelodysplastic syndromes, and certain solid tumors, such as melanoma and breast cancer.^(p78) Furthermore, KBA1413 has demonstrated potent antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC) *in vivo* and has been further engineered into a bispecific T-cell engager (BiTE) format to enhance its therapeutic potential.^(p78) These findings underscore the value of B-cell screening, particularly in the context of cancer survivors, in identifying novel TSAs and patient-derived antibodies.

The use of phage display technology for the discovery of TACA-targeting antibodies

Lastly, phage display technology is further propelling the discovery of anti-TACA antibodies by enabling the presentation of diverse antibody libraries on bacteriophage surfaces to rapidly identify paratopes for diverse targets.^(p79) Several studies have

successfully harnessed this technique to generate recombinant antibodies targeting TACA epitopes. For example, Kubota *et al.* developed novel anti-Tn single-chain variable fragment-fragment crystallizable (scFv-Fc) fusion proteins derived from a phage display library generated by immunizing mice with COSMC-deficient Jurkat cells.^(p80) Using an approach analogous to that of Kling Biotherapeutics, Mao *et al.* generated a phage display library from 20 cancer survivors and employed it to isolate human scFv antibodies against TACAs such as sialyl Lewis X, Lewis X, and GM3, although the resulting antibodies exhibited relatively low affinities.^(p81) Together, these studies show that multiple approaches involving phage display libraries can be used to successfully identify anti-TACA antibodies.

Further efforts to refine the specificity of anti-TACA antibodies have been made by engineering the antibody repertoires. For example, Schoonbroodt *et al.* engineered the heavy chain complementarity-determining region 3 (CDR3) to create a phage display Fab library enriched with antibodies that bind charged

carbohydrate epitopes such as sialic acid.^(p82) Moreover, the novel phage display library approach developed by Combotope Therapeutics (Kongens Lyngby, Denmark) further extends these advancements^(p33) by creating antibody libraries, where a TACA-specific heavy chain is combined with a diverse library of light chains using chain shuffling. This unique approach could enable the discovery of antibodies against a wide array of target glycoproteins as the scFvs retain specificity against the TACA moiety, but might exhibit additional specificity against other structural elements, such as surrounding amino acid residues.

Collectively, the abovementioned technological innovations in antigen generation and antibody discovery have provided an advanced toolbox for selectively targeting TACA epitopes. By integrating glycoprotein expression technologies, detailed structural elucidation, protein engineering, B-cell screening, and display methodologies, the development of more precise diagnostic tools and targeted therapeutics with improved efficacy and safety profiles in cancer treatment is now possible (Figure 3).

Ongoing challenges, opportunities, and concluding remarks

Despite recent technological and translational progress, several persistent challenges continue to limit the widespread clinical application of TACA-targeting antibodies. In particular, the low intrinsic affinity of antibodies for carbohydrate antigens remains a key limitation for developing efficacious TACA-targeting therapeutics. Unlike protein epitopes, which typically form deep pockets or structured surfaces for antibody engagement, TACAs, such as Tn and STn, are structurally compact and poorly immunogenic. Consequently, the generation of high-affinity antibodies with selective recognition of these moieties remains a significant challenge. Structural analyses of antibodies, such as 5E5 and L2A5, have shown that direct binding to Tn and STn residues is feasible; however, most candidates exhibit suboptimal specificity or depend predominantly on peptide-backbone interactions rather than direct glycan engagement. Overcoming these limitations will require comprehensive screening, structural elucidation, rational design, and glycan-focused affinity maturation, supported by increasingly sophisticated glycan engineering technologies.

A second major issue is tumor heterogeneity and resistance mechanisms that further compound this challenge. Expression of TAAs is highly variable across tumor subtypes and patient populations, and even within a single lesion.^(p2) Such variability limits the uniform applicability of monotherapies and might facilitate immune evasion through antigen loss. Targeting TACA-peptide epitopes, particularly on glycoproteins essential to tumor cell survival, could offer a strategic advantage by reducing the likelihood of escape through loss of a single antigen. However, systematic analyses to identify the most conserved and vital glycoproteins across cancer types are still lacking.

A third challenge closely related to the previous ones is the selection of optimal therapeutic targets. Although TACAs are typically absent or expressed at only minimal levels in healthy adult tissues, several exhibit substantial structural homology with glycans found on normal cells, particularly N-glycans, raising the

FIGURE 3

General workflow for discovery and optimization of antibodies targeting tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens. Schematic overview of recent strategies for the identification and engineering of anti-TACA antibodies. (1) Target selection: candidate TACAs are chosen based on tumor-specific glycosylation patterns and clinical relevance. (2) Antigen acquisition and preparation: TACAs are generated using sources such as glycoengineered SimpleCell lines, cancer cell lines, patient-derived tissues, or chemoenzymatically synthesized carbohydrate mimetics (e.g. CMPs). (3) Immunization and B-cell isolation: mice or other host systems are immunized with TACAs, or alternatively, B cells from cancer survivors with natural anti-TACA immunity are isolated. (4) Paratope discovery: antibody variable regions are identified via sequencing, single B-cell sorting, or phage display library selection. (5) Engineering and optimization: pre-existing antibodies, leads from immunization, or display libraries could undergo computational design to enhance affinity, specificity, or stability. (6) Primary screening: candidate antibodies are screened for TACA binding by ELISA/DELFA, surface plasmon resonance, or flow cytometry, and evaluated for binding strength and/or biological activity. (7) Hit-to-lead development: promising binders are further characterized for structural interactions, *in vitro* functional activity, and preclinical efficacy, leading toward therapeutic development.

risk of on-target, off-tumor toxicity. In addition, many of the most promising glycoprotein targets, including MUC1 and CD44, are broadly expressed in both healthy and malignant

tissues, achieving tumor selectivity only through cancer-associated aberrant glycosylation. Consequently, future targeting strategies must prioritize both the identification of suitable glycoproteins and epitope-level precision, discriminating the exact glycopeptide configuration present in cancer cells rather than targeting the protein or glycan in isolation. Recent advances in glycoproteomic profiling, including proteomic analyses of COSMC-deficient cell lines and novel glycan capture methodologies, are beginning to enable such refined target discovery and hold considerable promise for the rational design of next-generation therapeutics.^{(p65),(p66),(p83)}

Although several challenges persist, technological innovations in antigen presentation and antibody discovery continue to accelerate progress. Approaches like SimpleCell technology allow precise control over glycan structures presented during immunization, whereas patient-derived B-cell screening and carbohydrate-mimetic peptide (CMP) vaccines, particularly in combination with the use of phage display libraries, can provide researchers with paratope libraries having improved chances of discovering antibodies with specificity for aberrant glycoforms. These advances are expected to be further strengthened by emerging computational tools, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and generative protein design, that enable researchers to model glycan–protein–antibody interfaces *in silico*, which can be used to accelerate hit identification and de-risk early drug development.^{(p84),(p45)} Moreover, advanced therapeutic modalities, including CAR-T cells, CAR-NK cells, ADCs, and RICs, offer enhanced versatility and potency for targeting TACA–peptide epitopes. CAR-T cells targeting Tn-MUC1 and CD44v6 glycopeptides have demonstrated robust activity in pre-clinical models, and ADCs like the anti-STn therapeutic (ST1 ADC) of Siamab have shown efficacy in ovarian cancer xenografts.^{(p72),(p73),(p74),(p75),(p76),(p77),(p78),(p79),(p80),(p81),(p82),(p83),(p84),(p85),(p86)} The latter modalities also offer an opportunity to engage intracellular signaling pathways, modulate the immune microenvironment, and deliver cytotoxic agents in a tumor-selective fashion.

In conclusion, the field of TACA-targeting immunotherapies stands at an inflection point. Foundational studies have established the biological relevance and therapeutic potential of aberrant glycosylation in cancer. However, to overcome the current barriers of low affinity of TACA-targeting antibodies, tumor heterogeneity, and epitope specificity will require a multidisciplinary effort that integrates glycoscience, immunoengineering, structural biology, and clinical oncology. Nevertheless, the convergence of these fields is already beginning to yield a new generation of targeted therapies that might ultimately offer superior specificity, reduced toxicity, and improved durability of response in the treatment of solid tumors. These advances give hope that patients with cancer will have access to better treatments in the near future.

Authors' contributions

Both authors participated in the preparation, review, and approval of the manuscript.

Declarations of interest

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No other interests are declared.

Declaration of generative AI

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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